

Environmental Social Work in Sierra Leone: An Emerging Field of Practice

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Abstract:

The paper explores ways in which social workers in Sierra Leone can engage in environmental social work. In the broader context of the Global South, this relates to the results of contributions to global social impact, to develop more environmentally oriented social work practices. Environmental injustice is one of the issues that requires social workers to use holistic intervention methods to achieve environmental justice.

The paper argues for environmental justice and indigenous social work practice in Sierra Leone focused on natural resource management. The paper conducted an in-depth review of the literature on environmental law in Sierra Leone, as well as selected theoretical literature on social work. The paper identified a lack of interdisciplinary collaboration among professionals as well as a lack of social entrepreneurship among social workers in Sierra Leone. The paper recommends active promotion of solidarity and social economics by social workers through natural resource management and engagement in environmental justice. The systems and people in the environment theoretical framework provides a framework for social workers' engagement with environmental issues when addressing client problems (individual, group and community). The curriculum of schools of social work should include social ecology and environmental justice through postgraduate applied courses in corporate social responsibility (CSR), social impact assessment (SIA), public participation (PP).

Keywords: *Social work; Environmental degradation; Environmental Justice; Natural Resource Management; Man in the environment.*

Introduction

As agents of change, social work professionals go beyond providing therapeutic interventions for individuals, groups and communities to reduce poverty and open connections between livelihoods and service users. Social workers are also bold advocates for social justice and improving the social functioning of clients in their communities. The 1992 Rio de Janeiro Earth Summit, Agenda 21 advocates a global partnership for sustainable development and poverty reduction. Environmental sustainability

when nations commit creating environmental sustainability policies to combat climate change and carbon emissions is one of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In Sierra Leone and around the world, issues of sustainable management and environmental protection have become pressing issues. Within the profession, it can be argued that discussions of developmental social work and the indigenization of social work in Africa are inadequate without a focus on environmental sustainability. This comes against the backdrop

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of environmental degradation constantly becoming a growing threat due to resource extraction by enterprises with capitalist tendencies and poor people using their natural resources for their livelihood. Whenever people need resources, they turn to the environment. The role of social workers is to facilitate this process by ensuring positive relationships between people and their environment. People are agents of the environment; their problems arise when they try to interact with the environment; at this stage the intervention of social workers is required.

Environmental social work is an emerging field in Sierra Leone within the broader social work discipline that focuses on the intersection of environmental issues, social justice and human well-being (Ritter, L. (2017). In recent years, addressing environmental issues such as change climate change, environmental pollution and resource depletion, highlighted the need for social workers to be involved in sustainability and environmental justice efforts. Social workers, with their commitment to social justice and community well-being, are well positioned to promote environmental issues and promote sustainable practices (Coates, J and Gray, M. (2016). Guided by professional values and principles of social work, practitioners should be concerned with the distribution and enrichment of resources (fairness and equity), extraction (in relation to conflict resources and human rights) issues. Moreover, in the African context, social worker intervention methods target vulnerable communities that are using the natural environment for their livelihood activities.

Overview of Sierra Leone Environmental Protection Legislative Framework

Sierra Leone has a system of laws and regulations designed to protect the environment, conserve natural resources and promote sustainable development. However, challenges remain to the effective implementation and enforcement of these laws, particularly in the areas of enforcement, limited resources, and public

awareness. Further efforts are needed to strengthen environmental governance, improve regulatory compliance, and address emerging environmental issues.

The Environmental Protection Agency Act designates the Environmental Protection Agency as the primary regulatory body responsible for the management and protection of the environment in Sierra Leone. Environmental Protection Agency Act No. 15 of 2022 (“EPA 2022”). The Act, signed into law on September 6, 2022, was enacted to ensure the continuation of the activities of the Sierra Leone Environmental Protection Agency and to ensure more effective and efficient protection and management of the environment, as well as other related issues. The Environmental Protection Agency 2022 repealed and replaced the Environmental Protection Agency Act No. 11 of 2008, which established a corporate body known as the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), the principal and lead agency in all matters pertaining to and concerning environmental protection, regulatory mechanism, preventive measures. safety practices and policies (EPA, 2022).

Furthermore, the National Disaster Management Agency Act No. 3 of 2020, in addition to establishing the National Disaster Management Agency, was enacted to manage natural disasters and similar emergencies throughout Sierra Leone, to establish offices of the Agency throughout Sierra Leone, to establish national, regional, district and disaster management committees, establish a National Disaster Management Fund to provide funds for the prevention and management of natural disasters and similar emergencies throughout Sierra Leone, and to addressing other related issues (NDMA, 2020). In addition, Law No. 11 of 2012 was passed to establish the National Protected Areas Authority and the Nature Conservation Trust Fund to promote biodiversity conservation, wildlife management, research and the sale of ecosystem services in National Protected Areas. It also established the Office of National Protected Areas, which is charged with overseeing national parks and protected areas designated for conservation

purposes, with the aim of protecting fauna and flora in their natural state, promoting sustainable land use and environmental management. The Authority also ensures the protection of natural ecosystems and threatened biodiversity in Sierra Leone, including the establishment and maintenance of representative and sustainable specimens; manages national protected areas in accordance with national environmental policies and laws; oversee the management of local and private natural reserves throughout Sierra Leone, including zoos and wildlife rescue and rehabilitation centres; controls management of wildlife outside reserves; regulates the conservation and management of wildlife throughout Sierra Leone (NPAA, 2012).

Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA), which is a critical component of Sierra Leone's environmental regulatory system. Before receiving approval, projects with potential environmental impacts must undergo an EIA to assess and mitigate their environmental impacts. By criminalizing development projects carried out without environmental impact assessments, the law protects environmental justice. Moreover, while advocating for the mitigation of social and environmental impacts, the law also advocates for social justice. Therefore, social workers can effectively address this issue by advocating for mandatory social impact assessment (SIA) as part of EIA; as a legal requirement in promoting social and environmental justice (EIA, 2011).

Methodology

For this study, a qualitative research approach was used to explore environmental social work in Sierra Leone as an emerging discipline. A comprehensive literature review of environmental social work, sustainable development, and related topics was conducted to gain insight into key concepts, theories, and practices in the field. Academic articles, books, reports, policy documents, and environmental legislation were reviewed to explore ways in which social workers can contribute to environmental sustainability and advocate for environmental justice. The analysis focused on

identifying the role of social workers in promoting sustainability, addressing environmental injustice, and promoting environmentally sustainable practices.

Indigenisation of Social Work Inspired Social Work Curriculum Realignment

Jarvis (2013) notes that social work institutions contain academics and produce professionals who lack the capacity to “address the intersection of environmental justice, social work, and social justice.” This is a global phenomenon as social workers simply train professionals to become social workers, group workers and community workers. Ideally, social work educational institutions in Sierra Leone should reform their curriculum; integrate social ecology issues. It is evident that social work in Sierra Leone and beyond mainly concentrates on social issues and is not concerned with topics relating to the natural and physical environment (Duwane C. J. 2011). There is a growing need for social workers with environmental knowledge in Sierra Leone and the environment should be included in the knowledge base of social work. Social workers may be aware of environmental issues but tend to simply focus practically on the social environment, but with adequate training in environmental issues they can develop their understanding of the need for environmental justice when providing assistance to their clients. Duwane (2011) further states that “it is important that social work courses and field placements offer students opportunities to explore the connections between environmental justice and social work.” For social workers to become active participants in environmental justice in the future, they need to embrace Duwane's recommendation to incorporate interdisciplinary ideas into social work education.

Irwin (2001) argues that “separating the social from the natural, the biological and the scientific may be effective in establishing disciplinary boundaries and gaining professional recognition from practitioners in other disciplines, but such

a division of labor becomes deeply problematic when confronted with environmental issues.”(Irvine, 2001: 7). Jones P. (2006) agrees with Irwin, noting that “social work education should promote accessible scholarship and connect social work's long-standing values and commitments to social justice with environmental justice issues.” Environmental problems currently faced by social workers and their clients include, but are not limited to: recurrent droughts, environmental pollution in various forms that poses great risks to people's health and livelihoods, irresponsible extraction of natural resources that leads to population displacement and environmental degradation. It can therefore be argued that the current Bachelor of Social Work degree modules currently offered at Fourah Bay College, Njala University, Milton Margai Technical University and Ernest Bai Koroma University do not adequately address environmental issues such as equity and sustainable development. To enrich the training of social workers so they can better respond to issues of environmental justice and sustainability, social work departments should not have introduced applied social science courses such as social ecology, social impact assessment, public engagement, and corporate social responsibility. These courses will prepare and enrich graduates to address issues of environmental justice, ethical business, and environmental sustainability.

To solve both social and environmental problems, we need interaction between nature and society (Friibergh Workshop, 2000). This approach redefines the social worker as a social ecologist with deep knowledge of environmental research, policy and practice. Although social work is a global profession, its practice varies from time to time and from place to place. The problems that existed during the inception of social work are different from the social problems that social work faces. It can also be argued that social workers need to be diversified and local to fit into the African context. Kemp (2011) argues that by neglecting the field of environmental justice and not recognizing it as a bonafide professional identity, social workers are violating their own ethics. The principles of

social work assume responsibility for helping those in need, solving social problems and promoting social justice. From a social justice perspective, there is nothing to stop social workers from delving into environmental justice issues because social workers are committed to vulnerable people and communities. However, their intervention depends on knowledge of social ecology and interdisciplinary.

Social Entrepreneurship

Social workers must create professional institutions and platforms for advocacy. This could take the form of an environmental working group within the Sierra Leone Association of Social Workers (SLASW) or the formation of new environmental pressure organizations such as the Forum of Concerned Social Workers or Social Workers for Human Rights. In other related professions, Climate Environment and Forest Conservation, Consortium, Sierra Leone (CEFCO-SL); an advocacy non-governmental organization specializing in environmental management and sustainable development that supports livelihoods and natural resource management. If social workers are not able to form an organization that deals directly with environmental issues, collaboration can be established with organizations such as the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), National Disaster Management Agency (NDMA), etc. These coalitions will be designed to solving environmental problems. justice and natural resource management in an integrated manner.

Zapf (2009) notes that “forming interdisciplinary partnerships is an important and effective step toward achieving environmental justice.... in her practice she pays great attention to environmental issues.” Platforms such as World Environment Day and World Social Work Day (WSWD), National Tree Planting Day, African Child's Day can be used to initiate the dissemination of environmental protection strategies among the general population.

The strength of social work lies in its involvement in an interdisciplinary approach to solving problems in communities and promoting social justice. The profession is then best positioned to play an active role in the environmental justice movement and to bridge the gap between social and environmental justice (Paehlke R 2001).

This view motivates “the legitimate emergence of social scientists as one group among several stakeholders in achieving sustainability” (Cox D, Pawar M (2006).

Social work practitioners can extend this by engaging in social action aimed at legal reforms and environmental awareness, and by educating communities not to grant a “social license” to investors who do not implement their Environmental and Social Management Plans.

The participation of social workers in solving environmental problems should not be problematized. The social work environment is as old as the profession itself. Historically, Zapf (2009) states that Mary Richmond, the founder of social work, practiced a social systems approach to social work “person in environment,” that is, “visiting the client in his home environment.” This means that the founder of the profession recognized the importance of the physical environment and its connection to human poverty. Since then, social workers have been involved in solving environmental problems affecting people, although more attention has been paid to the narrow social and economic environment compared to the biophysical environment. Limited attention to the environment is one reason environmental justice issues receive little attention. The environmental crisis is one of the modern problems that poses a great threat not only to the poor, but also to rich people and communities.

Role of Social Workers in Environmental Advocacy

Social workers play a critical role in advocating for environmental justice and sustainability. They work to raise awareness of environmental

issues, mobilize communities to address environmental issues, and advocate for policies that promote sustainable practices. In terms of the knowledge base of the social work profession, the integrated approach to social work is the core standard. It covers human rights, global social development and environmental perspectives (Patel L (2005), guided by the conceptual framework of the environmental perspective. Environmental problems are symptoms of serious and fundamental problems, and their solution is through social, economic and political changes, rather than through scientific and technological changes. Balancing human impacts on the environment with its inherent needs is critical.

In the last decade, in line with the MDGs, concepts such as sustainability, social development and sustainable development have become widely used in social work, both in practice and in theory. These issues relate to what Midgley and Conley call developmental social work. Patel (2005) notes that social development is the setting of goals that lead to the improvement of people's material conditions or the achievement of socio-economic returns. This statement views social workers as agents for improving people's productive abilities by connecting them with the environment. Midgley and Conley note that social development approaches are also referred to as developmental social work, where social workers are primarily focused on improving the basic abilities or functioning of individuals, groups, and communities by addressing basic needs. Basic needs are environmental because individuals, groups and communities depend on the environment to meet their social and economic needs. In this case, the focus of social workers should be on ensuring that individuals, groups and communities use resources in a sustainable manner to ensure their livelihoods and the livelihoods of future generations.

Sustainable development means protecting people and the environment, and giving hope to future generations. Social work is, at its core, seen as a profession that gives people hope. It is “the fullest realization of the person-in-environment perspective” and is the theoretical

cornerstone of macro-level social work practice (NASW, 2000: 105). The Systems and Person in Environment approach takes a broad view of the social work person/client in relation to social, economic, political and natural environmental issues. Social workers usually tend to ignore the biophysical (natural) environment in the helping process. The document therefore calls on social workers to take practical steps towards holistic solving environmental problems by helping poor people.

Conclusion

In conclusion, environmental social work plays a vital role in promoting sustainability, advocating for environmental justice, and addressing complex issues related to environmental issues. Social workers have a unique opportunity to contribute to efforts to create a more sustainable and just world by integrating environmental considerations into their practice, advocating for policy change, and supporting communities affected by environmental problems. Going forward, it is vital that social workers continue to engage with environmental issues and work towards creating a more sustainable future for all. Ecological social work emphasizes the importance of integrating environmental perspectives into social work practice. Social workers are encouraged to consider the environmental context of social problems, assess the impact of environmental factors on individuals and communities, and incorporate environmental considerations into their interventions. Promoting sustainable practices in social work: Social workers can promote sustainability in their own practice by adopting environmentally friendly practices, reducing waste, and advocating for sustainable policies in their organizations. By modeling sustainable behaviour, social workers can inspire others to act towards a more sustainable future.

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